

OUR MASTER'S LIFE IS AN EXAMPLE FOR US

¹Ishakova Shaira Mirsodigovna, ²Fakhrutdinova Mashkura Fazliddinovna, ³Abdushukurova Zamira Zayniddinovna, ⁴Tursunov Latif Tursunovich

^{1,2,3}Department of Soil Science, National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

⁴We dedicate to the bright memories of our teacher Professor

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Abstract. *This article presents the scientific and pedagogical activities of the agricultural worker, doctor of biological sciences, Professor Latif Tursunov, as well as the memories of his colleagues and students about the teacher. During his lifetime, the teacher trained a number of students, who are currently working in all countries of the world. For nearly 50 years, Professor Latif Tursunov has been lecturing on all fields of soil science, conducting laboratory exercises with high pedagogical skills, and generously spreading his knowledge to young people. Latif Tursunov gave interesting lectures not only in Uzbekistan, but also in foreign countries - Czech Republic, Hungary, Egypt, China, Turkey. Prof. L. T. Tursunov's scientific research activity was especially effective during the years of independence.*

Keywords: *professor, science, mentor, lecture, foreign, soil, laboratory, scientific research, classes, university.*

To teach you a letter in the path of truth,
His face is an irreplaceable beauty.

A. Navoi

INTRODUCTION

The level of science and people of knowledge is set at a high level in every society. Our Uzbekistan, being the homeland of teachers, probably deserved such honorable names. In fact, if the father is the reason for the birth of a person, the teacher increases his knowledge by teaching him. In this world, there are few dedicated professionals who are happy with the success of their students like the teacher. Indeed, no one is more happy and full of joy in the happiness and prosperity of his student than his teacher.

When talking about a certain ruler, they asked about his mentor, and the attitude towards the ruler was different depending on his mentor. In particular, scholars who researched the history of Alexander the Great feel the need to study the science and history of his teacher, Aristotle. Like Amir Temur, Sahibqiran always respected his teacher Sayyid Baraka. In his place, Amir Temur's high victories were caused by the prayers of his teacher.

As fate would have it, a merchant and a scientist embarked on a long journey on the same ship. But a strong storm arose in the sea and the ship sank. All the property of the merchant and all the books of the scientist were drowned. The scientist and the merchant barely survived. Then both the merchant and the scientist began to cry. The scientist looked at the merchant and said, "Why are you crying? You survived yourself." Then the merchant said to the scientist, "Why are you crying, I lost all my property, I am left with nothing?" The scientist began to get even more upset, saying that my books were lost, and I wanted to leave the knowledge in the books to my students. The merchant said that your knowledge remained with you. There are many such beautiful examples for us in the lives of our scholars. One of our great scientists and mentors is Latif Tursunov, an agricultural

worker who served in Uzbekistan, doctor of biological sciences, professor Latif Tursunov, whose scientific work and life paths are an example for us.

Latif Tursunov was born on January 21, 1938 in Kattakorgan district of Samarkand region in a peasant family. He graduated from Kattakorgan Pedagogical Technical College with honors in 1957, entered the Department of Biology and Soil Science of Uzbekistan National (former Tashkent State) University and graduated with honors in 1962. This year L. Although Tursunov was recommended by the state certification commission for post-graduate studies, in order to further strengthen his knowledge, he entered the geography department of the university's geography faculty, specializing in soil science, and participated in scientific field expeditions organized in the Kashkadarya region under the leadership of the famous geographer Prof. Z.M. Akramov. Despite his young age, Latif Tursunov entered the graduate school of the All-Union Institute of Agrophysics in St. Petersburg and completed his scientific work ahead of schedule, continuing his work at the Department of Soil Science of the university.

In 1969, Ustoz received the scientific degree of candidate of science, in 1980, doctor of science, in 1973, associate professor, and in 1983, he received the title of professor.

As the sages say: "Enlightenment protects the world." Enlightenment leader Abdulla Avloni said in this regard: "The happiness of every nation, the peace and happiness of the state depends on the good education of the youth." Allama Imam A'zam's teachings were applied by the teacher: "Make it a habit to practice knowledge; if a scientist does not put his knowledge into practice, he is like a body without a soul." For nearly 50 years, Professor Latif Tursunov has been lecturing on all fields of soil science, conducting laboratory exercises with high pedagogical skills, and generously spreading his knowledge to young people.

Latif Tursunov gave interesting lectures not only in Uzbekistan, but also in foreign countries - Czech Republic, Hungary, Egypt, China, Turkey.

As long as a person is in need of knowledge, he is a scientist. If he thinks that he has learned, then his ignorance has begun. I would not be wrong to say that our professors were scientists in this sense, and they were great scientists who studied almost all the soils of the territory of Uzbekistan from all angles. In 1965, starting with the study of the water-physical properties of mountain soils, he conducted his first field research in extremely difficult conditions of the Karshi desert, the Bukhara oasis, the Karakol oasis, the soil of several districts of the Samarkand region, in the language of our people, "from thread to needle". The soils of Russia, especially the soils of the Novgorod region, were also studied in detail.

Prof. L. T. Tursunov's scientific research activity was especially effective during the years of independence. The soil of Mirzachol, Kattakorgan, Khatirchi, Nurota, Kitab, Shahrisabz districts of our Republic was studied by our Jonkuyar scientist, the credit maps were re-analyzed and handed over to farms. Worked effectively with foreign countries on practical and fundamental international projects. Under the leadership of L. Tursunov, a school of agrophysics and genetic soil science was created at the university. Under the guidance of the teacher, 25 candidates and 3 doctoral dissertations were prepared. It would not be wrong to say that today the teacher's students are working in this field in all countries of the world, that is, in the development of soil science and increasing the fertility of soils in all aspects.

As they say, a scientist without a book is a tree without fruit, L. Tursunov's 300 scientific-pedagogical, scientific, scientific-popular works, monographs, training manuals, textbooks reflect all the characteristics of the soils of Uzbekistan. The scientist's "Fundamentals of Soil Science"

(1976), "Soil Physics" (Parts I and II, 1982), "Soil Physics" textbook (1988), "Pochvennye usloviya oroshaemyx zemel zapadnoy chasti Uzbekistana" (monograph, 1981), "Pochvenno-fizicheskaya Characteristic territorial nizovev Amudari" (monograph in collaboration with S.Abdullaev, 1987) books are still considered the main educational literature for students today. Prof. L.Tursunov is a skilled organizer and leader and has been working as a vice-rector and head of the department for many years.

Academician J. Sattarov, who has made great contributions to the science of Uzbekistan with L. Tursunov, prominent and influential scientists of our republic, remembers like this:

I will start my memoirs about Latifjan with a quote by Hasan Basri: Scientists are like stars. If it is visible, people will find a way with them. If they lose sight and are left in the dark, they will wonder where to go. Academician J. Sattarov, who has made great contributions to the science of Uzbekistan with L. Tursunov, prominent and influential scientists of our republic, remembers like this:

My friend Latifjon and I graduated from the Pedagogical University with excellent grades and studied together at the Department of Soil Science and Agronomy of the Faculty of Biology and Soil Science of Tashkent State University. During this period, Latifjon gained great respect in front of his friends with his eloquence, generosity, humanity, modesty, and hard work, and was appointed as the captain of the course. On one of the bitterly cold days of winter, when Latifjon and I were coming from the village to the city to study in adhan, there was a 2 m deep ravine on one side of the road, and we both fell into this ravine. Perhaps we forgot that there was a ravine in our haste, or it was not visible because of the abundance of snow, we slipped over the ravine, barely managed to get out, and continued on our way. By this, I want to tell you about Latifjon's valuable character, his diligence in studying and his persistence. Latifjon and I both graduated from this faculty and got jobs in this faculty. We both defended our candidate and doctorate. L.Tursunov was awarded several times by our government for his services to science. I am proud that I was born and raised in the same village with such a person, that I learned while sitting at the same desk, that I studied in the same course and became a friend, that I served the people in the same line as a comrade in the same field of science.

Professor H.H. Tursunov, who worked side by side with them, remembered L. Tursunov as follows:

I am happy that we have been working side by side with L.Tursunov, our dear, kind, consultative friend and colleague, for many years. In the last years of our work together with L. Tursunov, soil scientists of our Republic published their monographs in the open press based on biographical analysis and the results of research on the laws of geographical distribution, genesis, evolution, ecology and fertility of soils of the Kashkadarya basin. The textbook "Soil Physics" is used as the main guide. He was one of the hardworking people who actively participated in the establishment of the faculty of soil science, soil physics and melioration, soil science, soil melioration and agrochemistry departments in our university and made a great contribution. Latifjon was distinguished by his diligence, thirst for science, demandingness, activeness in public works, modesty and kindness among friends. The professor was not only a skilled pedagogue, but also a loving family head together with his colleague and spouse Mamlakkhan. He raised each of his children to be educated and patriotic. A portrait of him stands on the desks of his students and colleagues as a dear teacher and good friend. May our mother earth, to which our friend devoted her whole life, shine a bright light on her in the hereafter. [1]

One of the closest students of our teacher L.T.Tursunov, doctor of agricultural sciences, professor S.Abdullaev remembers the teacher like this:

Even after the scientists passed away from this mortal world, his good deeds and works are always remembered with respect by his students who grew up under his guidance.

Latif Tursunov's entire academic career was inextricably linked with the work of the National University of Uzbekistan.

Today, the lessons given to my teacher advised him to continue scientific research in the development of the science of soil science, to raise its prospects to higher heights, to solve the problems in the field, to maintain, restore, increase and protect soil fertility, and in its implementation, the students are achieving high results. We students will never forget the teacher, we will continue their work and ask Allah to make their souls happy. It is a real happiness for us students to be born to people who leave a lasting memory.

Z. Jabbarov, one of his students who worked with Professor L. T. Tursunov for several years, now a professor, head of the Department of Soil Science, tells the following story:

Professor Latif Tursunov was not an ordinary scientist. Most importantly, he was a righteous scientist.

I saw them for the first time on the fourth floor, where the department is located, when I entered the Department of Soil Science in 1998. In the 3rd year, professor L.Tursunov gave a lecture on "Soil physics", he read the lecture in such a way that all the information was flowing from him like a spring. In their lectures, they used to say that I smell the soil and "talk" with it. When L. Tursunov was a 3rd-year student, they took me to a republic-wide conference, it was my first time to participate in a conference, and they added my last name to the thesis. The fact that I co-authored a thesis with a professor at the most prestigious university had a different effect on me, I thought that I would become a scientist like this teacher.

L.Tursunov understood well the young researchers doing science, when I was studying in the graduate school, they hired me for 2 projects that they were leading, because I would get help from all sides. They would take me to innovative exhibitions, conferences, expeditions, dissertation defenses, wherever they were, and give me advice on the secrets of life and science.

L. Tursunov united all professors and teachers in the department as if they were one family, and they called the female teachers of the department "girls". Every year, with the arrival of the spring season, they organized sumalak, and in the summer, they organized an expedition with the department's team at the end of the academic year. From them I learned harmony.

CONCLUSION

The only features of Professor L. Tursunov that are not found in other scientists were his high enthusiasm, he never stopped. At the same time, they would be busy in several places, with several different jobs. He wrote a lot of scientific projects, monographs, methodological manuals and scientific articles, and taught young people. People who saw him on the street thought that Professor L. Tursunov was ordinary, because he was a humble, noble, humble, sun-like person.

Our teacher Latif Tursunov, an agricultural worker who served in Uzbekistan, who was just as enthusiastic, thirsting for knowledge, always seeking knowledge and became a high-level scientist, would have turned 86 years old this year.

In this place, Ahnaf ibn Qays - "Scientists are great people who deserve respect." The saying that the result of any greatness that is not supported by knowledge is humiliation is just like what was written about our teacher.

Now we ourselves, along with teaching students, realize that the difficult and rewarding work of teaching science is not easy.

Our teacher Latif Tursunovich devoted his life to the study of our holy land, both religiously and secularly.

I wanted to end our article with the following poetic thoughts of one of our scholars, Orazii, because the whole life of Ustazim Latif Tursunovich Tursunov was devoted only to the study of science:

If the earth is a desert, a field of flowers is knowledge,
The stage world is divided by the science of art.
Science and science are armed together, the leader of science,
The arrow of knowledge does not harm any soul.

Our teacher would be 86 years old if he were alive now. Every time I give a lecture to students, I always point to my teacher as an example, I talk about how he was a humane and humble person, very hungry for knowledge. Even if it is a little, the souls of our teacher may be happy with this.

REFERENCES

1. Саттаров Ж.С., Фахрутдинова М.Ф., Исҳоқова Ш.М. Устозимиз профессор Л.Турсунов хақида. / Управление земельными ресурсами и их оценка: новые подходы и инновационные решения. Материалы российско-узбекской научно – практической конференции посвященной 100 летию национального Университета Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека. Москва –Ташкент, 2019. 59 – 64 б.
2. Исҳоқова Ш.М, Фахрутдинова М.Ф, Тўрабоев А. Устозимиз хотираси ҳамиша ёдимизда. Рисола. Т; 2020.
3. Турсунов Л. Ўзбекистоннинг тупрокшунос олимлари. Т; 2012.